

IPBES nexus assessment

Chapter 4, data management report 2

Identifying and assessing cross-cutting decision-support tools

Code: IPBES_NXS_4.2

Version: v2.0.0

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Description

This dataset of decision-support tools corresponds to the IPBES nexus Assessment chapter 4, section 4.4. The methodology explained in this report responds to the mandate of chapter 4 to assess decision-support tools that help address nexus challenges, including characteristics that describe (a) set nexus-relevant objectives and targets, (b) response option choices, and (c) scaling. Three sources of data were included in a systematic review to identify nexus-relevant decision-support tools: a systematic review of peer-reviewed literature, a grey literature review, and a nexus assessment call for relevant Indigenous and local knowledge (ILK) resources.

Process overview

Protocol

Type of analysis/search/review: ‘Systematic review of nexus-relevant decision-support tools’

Search languages: Chinese, English, Portuguese, Spanish

Search engines: Web of Science, Scopus, CNKI, Google Scholar

Exact search date: 3 January 2023 (peer-reviewed literature); 31 May - 15 June 2023 (grey literature); 18 July 2023 (ILK call)

Sample extracted: 741

Search terms: See (A) for the extended search terms used for the peer-reviewed literature (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_peerreviewed_search terms (A)) and (B) for the associated R code (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_searchterms_expansion_litsearchr (B).R) ; (C) for the extended search terms used for the grey literature review (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_greylit_search terms (C).pdf), and (D) for the extended search terms used for the ILK call (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_ILK (D).pdf). The Advanced Search function was used across each search engine and specified to capture the search terms present in the article title, abstract, or keywords. A period of publication was not specified for this review search. The original set of keywords were enhanced using the *litsearchr* package in R (Grames et al. 2019), which identified the strongest keyword connections and suggested additional keyword combinations based on the initial keyword combinations. Additionally, the grey literature review process was also improved upon via snowball recruitment, in which each reviewer contacted three experts from their respective country and area of expertise to solicit additional records.

In general, the logic behind keyword selection was that papers:

- i) were about a nature or biodiversity decision-support tools,
- ii) focused on at least one of the nexus dimensions that are the focus of the assessment

Fields extracted:

- Authors (AU)
- Title (TI)
- Abstract (AB)

Location and format of the data: (E) (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_originaldataset (E).xlsx)

Treatment applied: Expert screening of the original datasets. Abstracts and titles were screened out when explicit tools were not analysed, the article solely consisted of a literature review, theoretical discussions were the substance of the article, or exclusively academic exercises were undertaken.

Analysis of the data: 14 reviewers (lead and contributing authors) were recruited to review the abstracts of all peer-review papers for relevance. The website 'colandr' was used for the reviewers to view each abstract and suggest the papers' inclusion or exclusion. Additionally, 4 reviewers (contributing authors) were recruited to search and screen the grey literature review papers based on their language proficiencies (Chinese, English, Portuguese, or Spanish). Lastly, 2 reviewers were recruited to review and screen the papers generated from the ILK call.

Sample extracted: 204

Location and format of the data: (F)(IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_reviseddataset (F).xlsx)

Treatment applied: Expert review of the narrowed datasets for relevant tools (NOTE: in multiple cases, one paper contained more than one tool). Each paper was reviewed at full extent by one of the 14 reviewers. Articles were screened out when explicit tools were not analysed, the article solely consisted of a literature review, theoretical discussions were the substance of the article, or exclusively academic exercises were undertaken.

Analysis of the data: Key thematic areas were extracted using predefined fields and definitions in Google Forms (R1) (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_datacoding (R1).pdf).

Sample extracted: 203

Location and format of the data: (G) (IPBES_NXS_DMR_4.2_decision support tools_finaldataset (G))

Treatment applied: Expert review of the datasets by a second reviewer, in order to establish inter-rater reliability. Each paper was reviewed at full extent by an additional reviewer that was not previously assigned to that paper. Articles were screened for relevance based on past criteria and the extracted thematic areas were also assessed for relevance and accuracy between reviewers.

Analysis of the data: If changes were recommended by a reviewer, key thematic areas were manually suggested in a shared Google Sheet document and conferred by the Data Curators.

Files attached

ID	File name	File type	File size	Description
A	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_A_d ecision support tools_peerreview ed_search terms.pdf	.pdf	77 KB	Final search terms used to search the peer-reviewed literature databases.
B	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_B_d ecision support tools_searchterm s_expansion_litse archr.R	.R	7 KB	R script used to identify the strongest set of search terms and add new terms to the final set of search terms.
C	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_C_d ecision support tools_greylit_sea rch terms.pdf	.pdf	77 KB	Final search terms used to search the grey-literature database.
D	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_D_d ecision support tools_ILK.pdf	.pdf	87 KB	Final search terms used to search the ILK call.
E	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_E_d ecision support tools_originaldat aset.xlsx	.xlsx	211 KB	Original dataset collated from the literature review process.
F	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_F_de cision support tools_reviseddat aset.pdf	.pdf	145 KB	Revised dataset once screened by reviewers.
R1	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_R1_ decision support tools_datacoding .xlsx	.xlsx	68 KB	Codes and definitions assigned to each tool captured by this literature review.
R2	v2.0.0_IPBES_NX S_DMR_4.2_R2_ decision support tools_finaldatase t.xlsx	.xlsx	72 KB	Final dataset once screened by reviewers.

References

Grames, Eliza M., Andrew N. Stillman, Morgan W. Tingley, and Chris S. Elphick. 2019. "An Automated Approach to Identifying Search Terms for Systematic Reviews Using Keyword Co-Occurrence Networks." *Methods in Ecology and Evolution* 10 (10): 1645–54. <https://doi.org/10.1111/2041-210X.13268>.